

METHODOLOGY OF USING AUDIO AND VIDEO MATERIALS IN DEVELOPING DIALOGIC SPEECH

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Annotation

This article provides a scientific and theoretical analysis of the methodology for effectively using audio and video materials in developing dialogic speaking skills in foreign language lessons, particularly in English language teaching. The concept of dialogic speech and its importance in foreign language education are explained, and based on the experience of developed countries and modern research, the article demonstrates how audio and video materials positively influence the formation of students' communicative competence. The potential of audiovisual tools in creating an authentic communication environment, improving pronunciation, expanding vocabulary, and enhancing students' motivation to engage in conversation is supported by factual evidence. Additionally, the article discusses methodological considerations that need attention when using such materials, possible challenges that may arise, and ways to overcome them. In conclusion, it is emphasized that integrating audio and video materials into the teaching process is an effective method for developing dialogic speech, and the teacher's role and methodological competence play a crucial part in ensuring successful implementation.

Keywords: dialogic speech, audio materials, video materials, communicative competence, foreign language teaching methodology, audiovisual tools, communicative approach, authentic materials, dialogue.

In today's era of globalization and information technologies, the ability to communicate orally in a foreign language is considered an important communicative competence. In particular, dialogue-based speech (dialogic speech) enables foreign language learners to engage in effective communication in real-life situations. Various researchers define the concept of dialogic speech differently. For example, as R. B. Turapova notes, "Dialogic speech is the development of the ability to express one's ideas in the process of communication, understand the interlocutor, and maintain the conversation effectively." This definition clearly reflects the essence of dialogic speech—exchange of ideas and interactive communication skills. Developing dialogic speaking skills is an important task for foreign language learners, and this issue is viewed as one of the pressing problems of modern pedagogy. In particular, teaching students to

communicate freely in English is one of the key requirements of contemporary education.

Looking at Uzbekistan's example, in recent years, attention to oral communication in the foreign language teaching system has increased significantly. According to Presidential Resolution No. PQ-1875 adopted on December 10, 2012, foreign languages—primarily English—began to be taught from the first grade in general education schools. The resolution emphasizes teaching foreign languages at all levels of education with a focus on developing communicative competence and using the foreign language as a tool for practical communication. As a result, the state educational standards designate the development of listening comprehension and speaking skills as priority objectives. In higher education as well, graduates are required to demonstrate oral communication proficiency in a foreign language. However, the methodology for developing oral skills, particularly dialogic speech, has not yet been fully established, and research in this area continues in academic literature.

In the modern world, technologies are rapidly entering the field of education. The development of pedagogical technologies allows teachers to create and apply new instructional materials. As D. Larsen-Freeman and M. Anderson (2011) emphasize, technologies enrich learning materials and make the learning process more engaging for students. In particular, the introduction of audio and video tools animates lessons and can motivate learners to master all four language skills. Analyses show that in recent years, many teachers around the world have made the use of audiovisual materials—such as audio recordings, video clips, and multimedia applications—an integral part of their teaching practice. For example, after Malaysia introduced the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) in 2017, special attention began to be paid to assessing and developing speaking skills. Unlike before, the focus is no longer solely on grammar instruction; teachers are now required to assess students' speaking performance during every lesson. This, in turn, necessitates broader incorporation of audio and video materials into the instructional process, as such resources are expected to support the development of students' speaking skills.

The idea of using audio and video materials in teaching dialogic speech is not new. A look into the history of language teaching shows that in the mid-20th century, during the rise of the audio-lingual method, the use of dialogues played a central role. At the beginning of lessons, students learned dialogues by listening to audio recordings or repeating dialogues recited by the teacher. In the audio-

lingual approach, dialogues served as a tool for acquiring language structures through repetition and memorization. In contrast, today's communicative approach employs dialogues as models of authentic communication, encouraging learners to exchange ideas freely.

Currently, audio and video materials are not merely supplementary tools in language instruction but have become an integral part of an integrated methodology. Research indicates that such materials increase learners' interest and motivation toward language learning and significantly enhance their oral communication skills. For instance, C. Canning-Wilson (2000), after conducting a large-scale survey, found that students enjoy learning a foreign language through videos. It was revealed that learners understand and retain material better when they can both see and hear the situational context presented in the video. Similarly, in developed countries such as the United States and European nations, authentic audio recordings, film excerpts, and conversational videos are widely used in foreign language instruction. This experience is also valuable for Uzbekistan's education system. In recent years, multimedia applications such as Kids' English and supplementary audio CD/DVD materials integrated into textbooks serve as vivid examples of this trend.

Audiovisual methodology is primarily based on the idea of developing learners' listening and speaking skills simultaneously by exposing them to authentic foreign-language speech samples through audio and visual means. This approach affects two sensory analyzers involved in oral communication—the auditory and visual analyzers—at the same time. As a result, within a short period, the learner receives a large amount of linguistic information through two channels (hearing and seeing). Research indicates that in a learning process based on audio and video materials, new words and expressions are presented as an integrated image together with their context (intonation, gestures and facial expressions, situation). This facilitates students' retention of language units and their use in spoken communication.

Audiovisual methodology is based on the following principles: 1) taking oral speech (listening/speaking) as the main criterion during the lesson; 2) choosing the dialogue form as the structural foundation of teaching oral speech; 3) perceiving new language material primarily through listening (receiving it through audio); 4) repeated practice and incorporating newly heard words and expressions into active speech. These four principles constitute the basis of audiovisual methodology. According to this approach, an authentic dialogue or conversation is first presented to learners for listening; students listen several

times and grasp the pronunciation and intonation of linguistic units, after which they begin to use them in their own speech through repetition and discussion.

Research and practical experience have shown that the use of audio and video materials yields several positive outcomes in the development of dialogic speech. The most important of these outcomes are presented below:

Improvement of pronunciation and intonation - learners acquire correct pronunciation, stress, and intonation patterns by repeatedly listening to the speech of a native speaker and imitating it. For example, experiments conducted by M. Ogay showed that school-age learners mastered the correct pronunciation of speech sounds more quickly as a result of repeatedly listening to authentic dialogues. Similarly, Supiyati (2011), in her study, demonstrated through practical experimentation that the speaking skills of learners in English improved significantly with the help of audiovisual materials — learners showed much better results than the previous group in aspects such as pronouncing sounds correctly and completing sentences with proper intonation. As J. Harmer notes, if learners want to speak English fluently, they must acquire correct pronunciation and intonation, and for this, they need the opportunity to see and hear someone pronouncing the words correctly — and audio and video materials provide exactly this opportunity.

Vocabulary enrichment and improved retention - it has been established that learning new words and expressions through audiovisual tools becomes much easier and faster. The reason is that learners not only hear a new word or expression but also see it in a visual context — which creates an image-based connection in the mind. For example, in a study conducted by G. Kausar (2013) among university students in Pakistan, it was found that learning new vocabulary was significantly more effective with the help of audio-video materials. Students remembered the situation they had listened to and watched, and were able to recall the new words quickly later; therefore, the audiovisual approach was found to be very useful in reinforcing new vocabulary. C. Natoli (2011) also emphasizes that “when a person has seen and heard something, upon hearing its name later, the image appears in their mind, and they can easily talk about it.” Thus, video frames and audio imagery “embed” new words into the learner’s memory in a “real” sense through context and visual representation, making them easier to remember and increasing the likelihood of using them in spoken communication.

Increased confidence and motivation to communicate - as learners see that they can understand authentic speech in a foreign language and respond to it, their self-confidence and intrinsic motivation to learn the language grow stronger.

For example, conversations with upper-grade students who realized they had understood the dialogue in an audio clip showed that most learners consider their ability to comprehend what they hear in a foreign language a significant achievement, and this gives them the sense of confidence: “I can speak too.” Observations in Malaysia confirm this as well — after emphasis on oral speech was increased within the CEFR program, students’ interest and participation in lessons rose due to working with authentic video and audio materials. Likewise, in an experiment in Saudi Arabia, the use of YouTube videos significantly increased second language learners’ interest in interactive classroom participation: the visual input in videos encouraged them to engage more in communication. In other words, video materials “bring life” to speech activity and draw the learner into conversation — as a result, the learner begins to enjoy communication, which boosts intrinsic learning motivation.

The development of a set of communicative skills – when a lesson is organized using audio and video materials, not only dialogic speaking but also other skills such as listening comprehension, reading, and writing develop simultaneously. This is because an integrated approach is used in this process: the learner first listens and watches (listening), then expresses their ideas (speaking), and sometimes takes written notes or reads a text (reading, writing). As noted by Priya P. and co-authors (2024), lessons enriched with audiovisual technologies have a positive impact on children with various learning styles – through visual images and audio listening, the needs of visual, auditory, and kinesthetic (learning through movement) learners are met. Research shows that students who learn with audiovisual tools demonstrate better results not only in listening comprehension and speaking but also in reading and writing skills – because the process of learning a language becomes engaging and active in multiple dimensions.

Interactivity and a collaborative environment – video and audio materials often require group discussions, staging role plays as a team, and completing project tasks together. This strengthens the environment of cooperative learning among students. For example, based on a short video shown during the lesson, students divided into small groups can collaboratively discuss the “predict the continuation” task, write it in dialogue form, and then perform it. During such activities, each student engages in active communication, listens to each other’s ideas, and responds – which is the most essential condition for developing real dialogic speech. It is also possible to organize debates based on audiovisual materials (for instance, a discussion of a documentary film). In this process,

students express their opinions, ask questions, agree or disagree – that is, real communication takes place. Research shows that in such an interactive environment, language learners' pace of entering communication and their spontaneous reactions increase, meaning their ability to build dialogues improves.

Summarizing the above results, it becomes clear that audio and video materials are a powerful tool for developing dialogic speech skills in a foreign language. Importantly, not only individual studies but also teachers' practical observations confirm the advantages of this method. In particular, K. Kathirvel and H. Hashim (2020), summarizing several foreign experiences, conclude in their article that audio-visual materials free students from an inactive classroom environment and offer a practical method for teaching them to speak in real-life situations, resulting in increased communicative activity in lessons. In conclusion, it can be said that the use of audio and video tools develops students' ability to engage in communication in a multifaceted way and significantly accelerates their skill of freely building dialogues in a foreign language.

Alongside the positive outcomes achieved through the use of audio and video materials, there are also certain issues and limitations that should be considered when applying this methodological approach in practice. The following discussion highlights these aspects and offers possible solutions.

Effective use of audiovisual materials largely depends on the teacher's preparation and proper lesson organization. Even the most engaging video can be ineffective in the hands of an inexperienced teacher or one lacking sufficient methodological skills. For instance, some teachers may struggle to select video materials and use them for pedagogical purposes – not everyone can find videos that are appropriate for the lesson topic, students' age, and language level. Sometimes, even when the material is found, teachers may not know how to utilize it effectively in the lesson. Therefore, it is necessary to provide teachers with regular training on working with audiovisual technologies and to organize experience-sharing seminars. According to methodologists' recommendations, every foreign language teacher should improve their digital literacy, acquire the skills to search for relevant audio and video resources online, and adapt them to the lesson. In particular, teachers should receive guidance on how to use numerous free resources available on online platforms today – such as British Council, TED-Ed, and educational channels on YouTube.

When selecting audiovisual material for a lesson, it is crucial that its content and language level are appropriate for the students. Videos containing unfamiliar

or overly complex vocabulary, or topics that are alien to students, will not yield the expected results. In some cases, even if a good video clip is suitable in terms of topic, it may be linguistically above the learners' level. To address this issue, the teacher can use methods such as showing only a short segment of the video instead of the full version, or pre-teaching the key phrases before presenting the video. In addition, the technical quality of the video or audio material is very important – if the sound is low or the image quality is poor, students' comprehension will be hindered. Therefore, teachers should first check the quality of the material and, if necessary, provide subtitles. At the same time, it is important that the video is not too long – excessively long or off-topic videos can distract and bore students. Experts recommend working with short videos of no more than 5-7 minutes, as students' attention may decrease and following the content may become difficult during longer videos.

To prevent continuous screen viewing (watching videos) from negatively affecting students' health, it is necessary to maintain moderation and balance. For example, when working with young children, it is recommended not to show videos longer than 5–7 minutes and to limit the lesson to only one video segment. Excessively bright colors and rapidly changing frames can tire children and strain their eyes. Therefore, it is advised by methodologists to limit the time of audiovisual activity in each lesson, for instance to 10–15 minutes, and then alternate it with physical exercises or eye exercises. In addition, when showing a video collectively in class, it is important to ensure that all students can clearly see the screen and hear the sound – otherwise, some learners may be left out of the process.

Audio and video materials serve as a tool for developing dialogic speech, and their role should not be excessively exaggerated. That is, the main goal of the lesson – ensuring that students themselves speak – should not be forgotten. Sometimes showing too many videos can leave students in a spectator role and reduce the time available for active communication. Therefore, audiovisual materials should be considered as an auxiliary component of the lesson – the information gained through them should lead to subsequent student speaking activity. From a methodological perspective, the most appropriate approach is to use a video or audio clip as a “trigger for communication.” For example, after watching a video clip, students immediately engage in a discussion or role play. In this way, the video fulfills its purpose – it acts as a stimulus, and the student responds with dialogic speech activity. If students' activity is not observed after

using audio/video materials in the lesson, it indicates that the tool has been used incorrectly.

Successful implementation of the audiovisual methodology has been observed in the education systems of many developed countries. For instance, in the United Kingdom, specialists at the British Council have developed hundreds of video and audio materials for foreign language lessons, accompanied by methodological guidelines, and presented them to teachers. In language schools in the United States, language laboratories and multimedia labs have been used since the 1950s–60s – in these labs, each student listens individually via headphones and responds through a microphone, while the teacher records and analyzes their speech. Today, such laboratories have become more advanced, integrating computer technologies into interactive systems. For example, in some European countries, students participate in international videoconferences during lessons, communicating in real time with peers in other countries. Such experiences demonstrate that the deep integration of audiovisual technologies into language teaching is highly effective in developing students' communicative competence. Therefore, it is appropriate for our education system to study these foreign experiences and implement innovative approaches adapted to national conditions.

Summarizing the above discussions, it becomes evident that while the methodology of using audio and video materials opens vast opportunities for developing dialogic speech, its successful application requires a high level of methodological skill, thorough planning, and adaptability from the teacher. With the right approach, a lively, engaging, and multisensory learning environment created through audiovisual tools can elevate students' communicative abilities to a high level. Most importantly, such lessons foster a positive attitude toward learning a foreign language, increase student engagement and enthusiasm – which is a crucial factor ensuring the effectiveness of the learning process.

The use of audio and video materials in developing dialogic speech is a significant and promising direction in modern foreign language pedagogy. Analysis of research and best practices indicates that the audiovisual methodology provides learners with a real communication environment, bringing their foreign language speech closer to real-life situations. As a result, students acquire the skills to understand and express thoughts in a foreign language more quickly. Correct pronunciation and listening skills are formed through audio recordings, while video clips help learners acquire paralinguistic elements such

as gestures, facial expressions, and cultural context – laying the foundation for full and natural communication.

The evidence presented in the article confirms that audiovisual tools lead to positive changes, such as increased vocabulary, easier retention of oral speech constructions, enhanced self-confidence, and greater motivation to actively participate in lessons. Naturally, this process requires the teacher's leading role and thorough methodological preparation – audio and video materials are merely tools, while it is the teacher's skill that enriches their content and directs communication. Therefore, it is necessary to enhance teachers' qualifications in this area, organize specialized seminars and training sessions, and develop methodological guides.

In the future, the use of audio and video materials in foreign language teaching will continue to expand with new forms and technologies. For example, the application of virtual reality (VR) or interactive video technologies can immerse the learner in a fully simulated communication environment, elevating the development of dialogic speech to a new level. However, even under current conditions, significant achievements can be attained by correctly and effectively using simple audio recordings and videos for educational purposes

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